

Hagia Sophia

also known as “Ayasofya-i Kebîr Câmî-i Şerîfi”, “Ayasofya Müzesi”

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Entry tags: Constantinople, Cathedral, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Islamic Traditions, Orthodoxy, Religious Complex, Christianity, Christian, Christianity, Church, Church, Sunni Islam, Mosque, Language, Religious Place, Constantine, Basilica, Greek, Orthodox Christianity, Balkans, Orthodoxy

The monument of Hagia Sophia has been a sacred place both for Christianity and Islam, being also a museum. Built in Late Antiquity by Anthemius of Tralles and Isidore of Miletus, is considered as the latest great building of the ancient world.

Date Range: 537 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Istanbul, Turkey

Region tags: Balkans, Turkey

The monument of Hagia Sophia is located in the historical peninsula of Istanbul, also known as Constantinopolis.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

The society in which the religious place is located is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Formerly to the Holy Trinity, nowadays to Allah.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

- Specialized labourers/craftspeople
- Other [specify]: The emperor Justinian

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– I don't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

- King or emperor
- Other [specify]: Justinian I

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation

Type of elevation

- Hill

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

- Yes

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

- Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

- No

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

- No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: H. B. Dewing, Glanville Downey, edd., Procopius (7 voll. Londinii: Heinemann, 1914-1940. Loeb Classical Library) vol. 7 Buildings

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- I don't know

Has this place been looted:

- Yes

Notes: During the 4th Crusade.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://muze.gen.tr/muze-detay/ayasofya>
- Source 2 Description: Official information on the current status of the monument

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

- Yes

↳ A group of features:

- Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

- No

↳ A single structure

- No

↳ One single feature

- Purposefully placed plants

↳ A group of structures:

- Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No
- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - No
- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes
- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes
- ↳ In antiquity
 - More than once
- ↳ In modernity
 - (European) Post-Renaissance
 - Other (date-range):: 19th century
- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
 - Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship
- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Roman brick

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 60

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 50

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 80

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Lime

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Marble

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

- ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

- ↳ Are the inscriptions a formal dedication:

– Yes

- ↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Names of caliphs

Notes: Names of Muhammad, Abu Bakr, Umar, Uthman, Ali, Hüseyin and Hasan

- ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

- ↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Medallions

- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

- ↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

- ↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

- ↳ On the outside:
 - Yes
- ↳ On the inside:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
 - Yes
 - ↳ Floral motifs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Mosaics
- ↳ Are there statues present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there paintings present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:
 - No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No other

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Seraph

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– I don't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Medallions

Iconography

Are there distinct features of the iconography:

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Names

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: Ottoman Sultans

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No other

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– I don't know

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Supernatural Beings

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god present:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Do they have another type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Do they have kin relation with elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ other:

– Other [specify]: Many Christians still consider this place as a church, therefore believe in the presence of the Holy Trinity in it.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: No other

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 200

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Daily

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: Money, incense

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Religious Specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– I don't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

↳ Present full time

– I don't know

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Men

Bureaucracy

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No